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Unexpected Sacredness: On Receiving Talismans As Gifts

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Preamble: An Unusual Chinese New Year's Eve

New Taipei City, Chinese New Year's Eve 2025. Two days later, I was to return to Europe after five months of fieldwork in Taipei and Keelung. My emotions were mixed: relief at seeing or syncing with my family, close friends, and partner; sadness at leaving Taipei and my Taiwanese friends; regret that my fieldwork felt not yet “mature” enough for another long pause. This time, my ethnography was especially challenging—my study of deconsecrating rituals to reveal gaps in museum archives on Chinese folk god statues touched taboo topics.

Abandoning or deconsecrating statues of gods is considered a source of bad luck, as it can make the gods resentful and vengeful, and attract other spiritual forces—such as ghosts—within the statues, which can be potentially harmful. Abandoning and deconsecrating statues are also signs of disrespect and ungratefulness towards the gods' protection.

Fig. 1: View from above of a mountain temple in Hsinqu, near Xinzhuang. Mr. Lin Sr. brought me here as an example of temples built to offer refuge to abandoned god statues. This practice, once performed during migrations, gained moral significance during Taiwan's Lottery Era in the late 1980s, when gamblers asked gods for lucky numbers and discarded them if they were unsuccessful. Photo by the author.

Despite these negative beliefs and feelings for discarded god statues, deconsecration rituals are becoming essential in daily religious practice due to the challenges of guaranteeing daily offerings and worship within modern life conditions (office hours, fire alarms in story buildings, and other neighborhoods' regulations that impact lighting incense for gods, etc.). Discussing this topic, nevertheless, is a source of embarrassment and discomfort for many Taiwanese. Fieldwork companions who had been supportive of my research inquiries in previous stays had ghosted me or reluctantly answered my timid questions on the topic. I had to change my fieldwork site, adopt a case-by-case methodology, and focus on ritual practitioners only, constantly experiencing a sense of precarity in the development of my field research.

Fig. 2: Shrine for an abandoned god—a Tudigong, or earth god—found on Heping Island near Keelung. Visible signs of decay include a missing moustache and crumbling paint. Photo by the author.

In this state of mind, I visited the Lin family:[1] father (Mr. Lin Sr.) and son (Mr. Lin Jr.), whom I met four years ago as key members of a temple I was then researching. Mr. Lin Jr., a Daoist priest in New Taipei, works with the support of his father, a devoted Guanyin (the *bodhisattva* of compassion) follower passionate about temple history and religious studies in Taiwan.[2] Their private shrine welcomes acquaintances and friends for

worship and provides protective talismans for the latter and Mr. Lin Jr.'s clients. Passersby often pause at Mr. Lin Sr.'s entrance, peering through the glass, hoping for Guanyin's blessings.

Four years ago, it was from one of the first conversations I had with Mr. Lin Jr. and Sr., in front of their private shrine, that I first learned about the topics of abandonment, discard, and deconsecration of Chinese folk religious statues. The two men had been particularly supportive of my research topic, and unlike other fieldwork acquaintances, they had continued to welcome me and consider me part of their lives. Mr. Lin Sr. was in favor of my academic dreams, as he himself wished for a scientific approach to religious studies for himself and his son. Mr. Lin Jr. accepted my request to meet over a cup of tea, as he somehow perceived I was not like other academics he had met before, who bombarded him with questions and then disappeared.

Grateful for their trust and goodwill, I wanted to express my gratitude by bringing festive food and red envelopes for the Chinese New Year. Mr. Lin Jr., after greeting me and declining any red envelope, revealed he had consecrated a Five Thunder Talisman (*wuleifu*, 五雷符) for me as I was about to leave for Europe. This talisman embodies five Marshal Gods of the Thunder Department, within Daoist pantheon, believed to guard against evil and misfortune, cure illnesses and bring wealth. It is usually hung on a wall at home. Days before our farewell, Mr. Lin Jr. commented on my small *qi* (氣) tattoo on my right wrist, saying I needed better protection. I never expected he would prepare a talisman for me, consecrated with blood from a small wound on a white chicken's crest, mixed with cinnabar and used to dot statues during rituals; the chicken is then released and not touched again. "What I did is no different from consecrating a god statue. This talisman embodies the gods' spirits, and they will descend to protect you when needed," Mr. Lin Jr. said with a smile.

This unexpected turn during the Chinese New Year's Eve constituted somehow an "aha-moment." It prompted me to consider a core argument in my reflection: sacred gifts are not simply tokens of gratitude but play a crucial mediating role in the ethnographic relationship and influence our understanding of the field. Not only did I perceive more distinctively and all of a sudden, the tribulations of worshippers I interviewed—turning upside down my "role" of ethnographer, if I ever had a role—but I also received the opportunity to reflect on my fieldwork in the following months from different angles. I had previously received several gifts related to my research, including books about the history of temples I studied or Buddhist lineages connected with religious museums of interest, as well as small sutras, small talismans and souvenirs produced in temples. However, until that Chinese New Year's Eve, I never reflected on the spiritually mediated importance of these gifts. How can these gifts help to mediate my relationship with and understanding of the field?

Gift-giving Sacred Materials: An Underexplored Topic

In this essay, I reflect on the sacred items given as gifts to ethnographers by their fieldwork collaborators. The ethnographer often becomes part of the interlocutors' families or social circles, with exchanges that denote intimacy and familiarity. As part of these relationships, ethnographers receive gifts—especially food—as signs of affection. In return, ethnographers reciprocate with gifts or monetary donations, particularly in contexts with marked economic disparities, sometimes continuing these obligations long after leaving the field (**Sliwinski** 2024).

It should not come as a surprise, then, that anthropologists researching religion might receive something more than food (**Garcia Probert** 2025; **Gillson** 2024). During informal conversations with my colleagues, I realized that my episode with Mr. Lin Jr. was not an isolated event. They also received amulets or deconsecrated gods' statues as a means to protect themselves during their work or, conversely, to show religious artefacts to their academic fellows and audiences and, consequently, spread research participants' knowledge abroad.

Receiving a sacred gift, such as my talisman, reminds me of two dimensions in material religion research and, more broadly, the anthropology of religion. First, sacred presences are not merely research objects, but an integral part of our ethnographic relationships with collaborators. Engaging with these forces reveals how we connect with our field and the people we encounter. This is clear among Taiwanese colleagues studying Chinese folk religion. During my first months in Taiwan in 2017, my local friends suggested that, although I do not believe in Chinese folk religion and was baptized Roman Catholic as a child, I should worship the fieldwork temple gods to receive their “informed consent.” They explained that Taiwanese scholars also typically do this.

Secondly, receiving sacred presences as gifts reminds us of our scholarly difficulty in representing and curating these material presences in contexts other than our ethnographic relationship. Despite the centrality of these two dimensions—the intersubjectivity of the sacred and its negotiation in scholarly and curatorial works—sacred gifts are seldom problematized in our debate as tools through which to reflect upon our positionalities, ethics, and analysis, but are kept as marginalia and anecdotes. What do these gifts add to museum and private collections, as well as research practice more broadly (**Gillson** 2024)?

Talismanic Bonds: An Overview

Talismans in Chinese folk religion (*fu* 符) are special sacred embodiments. They are assemblages of sacred materials, such as incense ashes taken from god's incense burner, coins, etc., and, more importantly, a talismanic script. The latter is an ensemble of symbols and characters with healing or apotropaic purposes, either painted on the

talisman or on a paper that is folded and inserted inside the talisman. The characters of the talismanic script are believed to attract and express cosmic forces due to their symbolic resemblances (cfr. **Robson** 2008, **Steavu** 2019).

Talismanic scripts are usually created by Daoist priests or spirit mediums (*tongji* 童乩). They combine characters, visual images, and structured graphic elements that represent the divine words and spells. These scripts follow fixed patterns, which specify the god involved, the function of the talisman (such as protection or exorcising evil), its effectiveness, and its area of application (**Chang** 2007). The scripts often appear unintelligible because the characters are deliberately altered; this obscurity is what gives them authority, as only ritual specialists can interpret them. Similar to god statue consecration rituals (**Reich** 2024), talismans are made effective through the specialist's spiritual cultivation, including purification, recitation of spells, hand gestures (mudras), and bestowal of vital energy (qi, 氣). Through these efforts, talismans become a medium connecting the wishes of the worshipper, the ritualist's skill, and the gods' power.

Fu can have various dimensions and supports; the most widespread and well-known ones are fabric *fu*, also known as *pingan fu* (平安符), or lucky talismans. These fabric talismans are typically provided after worshippers have made offerings to the main or specific deity of the temple, consulting the deity through divination blocks to obtain approval for granting worshippers protection. After worship, worshippers make a donation to the temple and can take the talisman, which is usually tied to bags and suitcases.

Fig. 3: A display of pingan fu taken from various Tudigong temples within the Taoyuan Tudigong Culture Museum (桃園市土地公文化館). Photo by author, courtesy of Taoyuan Tudigong Culture Museum.

Certain talismans are used as ointments, drunk with decoctions, or used for washing worshippers' bodies. They can have various degrees of personalization, depending on

worshippers' requests or special relationships with either gods or ritual specialists (**Chang 2007**).

In Chinese folk religion, talismans, like statues modeled after a temple's main god—the “mother” god—are periodically recharged. This is done by bringing them to the temple's incense burner, which is believed to renew their spiritual power sourced from the gods. Such renewal typically occurs annually (**Chang 2006**).^[3]

Because talismans are sacred objects intended for worshippers' protection, there are several taboos associated with their use. These include avoiding contact with dirty substances or places, not sharing or transferring them (as this disrespects the gods protecting the worshipper), and disposing of them in certain ways—for example, first asking the main god for permission and giving thanks before burning the talisman with paper money. These taboos can vary depending on the type of talisman the worshipper has, reflecting the complex relationship between ritual and the meaning attributed to these objects.

The talisman I received from Mr. Lin Jr. consists of two distinct layers: the talisman itself and a written note from Mr. Lin Jr. that explains the context in which the talisman was provided. The talisman is written on a Heavenly Emperor's Gold (*tianjin*, 天金), a paper money used for the worship of the Heavenly Emperor (*Tiangong* 天公), the supreme god that rules the universe. The talisman is composed of five Generals of the Thunder Department, who assist the god Xuantian Shangdi (玄天上帝), the Northern Emperor, associated with the element of water and believed to control water and extinguish fire, therefore, to prevent and protect from disasters. The Thunder Department has thirty-six Generals; therefore, the combination of Generals selected for the talisman may vary depending on the specific functions desired by the worshipper and the Daoist priest. The spatial disposition of the Generals reflects a hierarchy between the Generals' functions. My talisman combines Marshal Yin (殷元帥)—who rules over the year, oversees human fortunes and misfortunes and assists in deterring evil spirits—at the center, with Marshals Zhao (趙元帥) and Wen (溫元帥)—two plague gods responsible, respectively, of guaranteeing wealth and exorcising evil and eliminating plagues—on the upper-left and upper-right corners, and Marshals Ma (馬元帥) and Kang (康元帥)—responsible, respectively, to bring peace and good fortune and to subdue demons—on the lower-left and lower-right corners. Each Marshal is dotted with chicken blood at the center and accompanied by seals (*yin* 印). Seals certify the authority and power of both the talisman and the Daoist priest—as attesting the validation of the ritual for making the talisman by and presence of the gods invoked by the seal—and have further talismanic functions. For instance, the talisman has two pairs of seals which, respectively, represent the Thunder Department as the Marshal's source of authority and the personal seal of Mr. Lin Jr. that certifies that he made the talisman.

These seals are reproduced alongside the yellow messages, which serve as a second level of reading. On the right side, it is mentioned that I paid respect to the family's shrine, while on the left, it is stated that Mr. Lin respectfully wrote this information on an auspicious date. Above, it is mentioned that the Daoist written source consulted and invoked for the consecration of the Five Thunder Talisman (‘‘Celestial Master’s Talisman,’’ 天師符籙), whereas below, the characters *zhenghu* (鎮護) and *pinhan* (平安) connote the function of the talisman to protect and guarantee peace to its owner.

Fig. 4: The talisman made by Mr. Lin Jr. for me with the divination blocks he gave me for interrogating the Thunder Generals (see after in this post), Photo by the author.

Fig. 4a: A screenshot of the explanation of the talisman provided by Mr Lin Jr. and Sr. through LINE. The characters reported indicated the names of the Generals.

The talisman connects me, Mr. Lin, and the main god of his family's shrine, confirming that my fieldwork was supported through both human and divine ties. Like any other

participant, the Lin family's Guanyin acknowledges my respectful visit and interest in her worshippers, Mr. Lin Jr. and Sr., by inspiring Mr. Lin Jr. to give me a strong protective talisman. This gift extended our ethnographic bond and allowed Mr. Lin Jr. and Guanyin to help deepen my understanding of material religion and how sacred artefacts are treated outside of ritual practice.

Handling with Care: The Journey of the Talisman

By the time I received the talisman, I had become more sensitive and careful around sacred materials than I was before. Throughout the five months of fieldwork, I heard many stories about the dangers associated with improper worship of god statues and the sense of responsibility that descendants or family members often feel when inheriting such statues from their parents or other family members. These stories even involved local scholars as protagonists. One day, a Taiwanese professor told me that, after acquiring deconsecrated god statues and ancestors' tablets from a student and using them as teaching materials during his lectures, he experienced a series of unfortunate events, prompting him to consult a Daoist priest for purification of his personal collection. Due to these narratives, I felt a sense of insecurity in receiving sacred materials from my fieldwork collaborators, as both a recipient of *materia sacra* and a scholar who could eventually use the latter for research and teaching purposes. The double source of worries—related to the talisman itself and my researcher's positionality—was central and has crucially shaped my reflections and practices during the last period of fieldwork and beyond.

Receiving such a potent talisman from Mr. Lin Jr. did not happen in a vacuum. Instead, it connected with other events in which I received sacred gifts. For example, one day, the uncle of one of my best friends in Taiwan, Yuhua, donated three *pingan fu* to me. He had served as a committee member at the temple where the donation originated. I received the talismans after an interview with him, following his participation in the temple's pilgrimage to southern Taiwan in the fall of 2024. Yuhua's uncle wanted me to have the talismans for my health and the success of my research, as the god of literature, Wenchang Wang (文昌王), was one of the three gods associated with them. I accidentally washed the talisman of Baosheng Dadi (保生大帝), the god of medicine, with my laundry. I had left it in my jacket pocket since my last visit with Yuhua's uncle. Panicking, I asked Yuhua for advice to fix the incident. She suggested I dry the talisman and bring it to her temple, Baoyuan Gong (保元宮). Although Baowang was not the same as Chifu Wangye (池府王爺), a plague god and the main god worshipped at the temple, she thought their ritual functions could complement each other. She said it might be possible to renew Baowang's talisman there. I followed Yuhua's suggestions and renewed the talismans' power before leaving for Europe.

Fig. 5: The pingan fu that I received from Yuhua's uncle that was accidentally washed with my laundry. Photo by the author.

The incident with the *pingan fu* happened just a few days before the meeting with the Lin family. It made me insecure about receiving the talisman from Mr. Lin Jr. That day, I hid

my emotions to avoid seeming ungrateful toward Mr. Lin Jr.'s generosity. Instead, I turned my anxiety into a question. "Could you please let me know how I should treat this talisman? I do not want to lack respect towards Thunder Generals," I said while internally sweating with worry. "Well, you do not need to reserve special treatment for them, but if you insist... Just put it on a shelf at your place and, when you prepare your meals, you can put them in front of it for a while to let them enjoy food and drinks with you," Mr. Lin Jr. concluded, as Mr. Lin Sr. nodded in approval.

My question to Mr. Lin Jr. was, after all, similar to what had begun the research inquiry for my entire postdoctoral project. How can god statues—especially if their provenance is unclear—be respectfully treated in museums? However, I also asked that question to disguise my uncanny feelings of anxiety. This reflected my difficulties in reconciling my positionality as a researcher with my own religious identity. I became interested in material religion and anthropology of religion partly to distance myself from my upbringing. The pervasive Roman Catholic influence in Italian society and my paternal family's devotion, including a great-great-uncle who was a priest, shaped this reaction. Given my agnosticism and "scientific glasses," why should I worry about material religion besides showing some respect to those who profess religion(s)?

With time and distance from the fieldwork, I confronted the responsibilities that came with possessing the talisman. I realized it evoked a sense of reverence I had learned as a child. This feeling guided how I curated the talisman after returning to the Czech Republic to complete the fellowship. My personal experience with religion, combined with the knowledge and empathy gained during fieldwork, shaped how I questioned the appropriate way to display and interact with the talisman and other sacred materials gifted to me.

I was ill-prepared to welcome such a talisman in my life. I currently live in a studio flat. The living room, bedroom, and kitchen share the same space. In my opinion, these are not suitable places for the talisman, as there is no separate room to keep mundane activities, such as eating or sleeping, apart from a sacred icon. For this reason, I decided to store it in my shared office, on one of the highest levels of my bookshelf. However, I do not go to the office every day. I cannot access the building on weekends and may be absent for business travel or health reasons. My office is also shared with a colleague, which changes the personal circumstances in which I received the talisman. Mr. Lin Jr. called the Thunder Generals to protect me, based on the trust built during years of fieldwork. Would the gods—and Mr. Lin Jr.—accept protecting me in a space I share with a stranger?

In the meantime, the **Research Cluster on Anthropology Advancements**, supervised by my postdoctoral supervisor, developed the idea of hosting a small exhibition on the topic of "wealth" across Asia as part of the **European Researchers' Night event**. My

talisman—on which I spoke during a presentation of my research to the Cluster—was considered by participants to be a good example of a guarantor of wealth and protection according to Chinese folk religion.

The request of the Cluster's members made my ethical concerns about the talisman and other artefacts I received concrete. Was it appropriate to transform the talisman into a research artefact, something I could publicly share with others, not only within publications, but also in more sensually mediated events such as an exhibition or a teaching session? Mr. Lin Jr. and Sr., as well as other fieldwork interlocutors, often said that they were happy to share their knowledge and experience with me, as they were convinced of the value of my research and the importance of having clearer ideas about Chinese folk religion. How about sharing a sacred artefact that was donated as a personal gift, however? Could my academic interest in the talisman as a “research sample” compromise my human bond and trust with Mr. Lin Jr. and Sr.?

Reflecting on the months spent with the talisman and the request to use it as an exhibition item, I saw several interrelated responsibilities. They evoked the strong emotion of fear I felt in the field. The first layer of responsibility was the trust I built with family Lin, reflecting broader intersubjective dynamics in Taiwan. Spiritual forces play a central role in shaping and negotiating relationships in Taiwan, and my ethnographic bonds were no exception. From the start, I had to negotiate my presence with Chinese folk gods, seeking their consent. The trust with fieldwork interlocutors was built on spiritual trust. Sacred gifts, therefore, reflected the double nature of my ethnographic bonds. Being responsible for a sacred artefact also meant caring for my relationship with fieldwork interlocutors and friends. What would happen if I accidentally mistreated the talisman? Considering the spiritual aspect of my research merely analytically would be short-sighted. I need to think again about my religious identity and positionality, and negotiate them with my interlocutors.

The second and core level of responsibility involved resurfacing the fieldwork on deconsecration rituals, a taboo topic, which I conducted over five months. Although I tried my best to mitigate the discomfort of my interlocutors in sharing their experiences about the topic, I still felt responsible for choosing such a controversial topic. The talisman—donated in circumstances of trust and friendship—and its challenges in engaging with it, *far away* from family Lin was a prelude to further hardships in representing—through publications and teaching—and curating research on a taboo topic. I perceived exhibiting, curating, and publishing about sacred matters as a transition (**Svašek** 2012, quoted by **Gillson** 2024) of meaning and purpose. Displaying the talisman or anything derived from my research on deconsecration was not a way to reify it, and consequently, to reduce my relationship with family Lin and other fieldwork interlocutors—mediated by gods—a “dry data”? Would gods be offended by my gesture, as they were in the case of the Taiwanese professor I described above?

Following these reflections, I decided to bring it with me when my university granted a one-month extension for my fieldwork in July 2025. I also added the talismans I received from Yuhua's uncle to my suitcase, applying a similar logic of renewing the power of sacred materials while checking on their status.

Fig. 6: I reactivated the power of the talismans I received from Yuhua's uncle at Baoyuan Gong (保元宮) in Xinzhuang, July 2025, during the main god Chifu Wangye's (池府王爺) birthday festival. Photo by Yuhua Chang.

Bringing sacred gifts back and forth served both to verify the appropriate means of storing and displaying them and to seek approval of their use as teaching and research materials, and to renew my trust in gods and humans.

In a morning hit by typhoons, I asked Mr. Lin Jr. to check Thunder Generals to see whether they were happy to have followed me all those months. He decided to place the talisman on the shrine's altar, allowing it to recharge its power by the incense burner. It seemed that everything was fine, and I did not disappoint the gods. Subsequently, I explained my moral concerns to Mr. Lin Jr. about displaying my talisman during the Researchers' Night.

Fig. 7: The talisman lying on the Lin family altar, July 2025. Photo by the author, courtesy of the Lin family.

Thunder Generals were not different from human fieldwork collaborators, to whom we must ask whether they wish to be named in our publications. Since it was a decision that the Thunder Generals should make, he suggested that I consult with them as I would have in any other Taiwanese temple, using divination blocks or two coins in lieu of the latter. After a pause, he decided to give me two small divination blocks he had collected. Returning to Europe, the five Thunder Generals agreed to participate in the

event, and that strangers would see them in my absence—the event dates coincided with a conference I had been invited to attend. My recommendation to offer Taiwanese snacks I had bought for the event, along with the request to handle everything with a pair of gloves and locate the talisman in a safe and elevated position, seemed to make the Thunder Generals content, as the Cluster’s members did not register anything anomalous.

On a personal level, caring for the talisman alleviated my sense of discomfort derived from researching controversial and highly charged affective practices, such as the disposal of sacred items. In resonating with my fieldwork interlocutors’ anxieties about the talisman, I was introjecting a certain sensitivity that helps me build trust with them in more recent and future fieldwork stays. On a research level, caring for the talisman reoriented my methodology, more consciously including gods as part of the ethnographic consent. This negotiation between my research, human, and religious identity is still ongoing. I am unsure whether some methodological choices—such as mainly utilizing drawings rather than photos in my online exhibition—are the most suitable ones for publicly approaching a taboo topic, but the level of reflexivity I have in designing them would not have been the same without the presence of the talisman in my life.

I still photograph, from time to time, the meals I offer to the Thunder Generals and share them in the common chat I have with family Lin. While their emoticons of approval relieve me each time, I often think about how the talisman serves as an incentive to maintain our ethnographic and human bonds despite distance.

Conclusions

In this contribution, I sketched the relationship I have developed with a talisman I received as a gift from a key fieldwork collaborator. This is part of a broader attempt to negotiate my identity as a researcher and non-believer in Chinese folk religion with the talisman’s sacred forces and other sacred materials I received during fieldwork. Thanks to the talisman, I had the opportunity to reconsider other spiritually-charged gifts I received from fieldwork collaborators with new eyes, as well as my positionality as researcher and personal religious background.

This collection, born from fieldwork relationships rather than independently initiated by me, has multi-layered meanings in my work. On the one hand, it serves as an attestation of trust and a continuation of a relationship that was born and nurtured during fieldwork. The sacred dimension of the talisman and other artefacts I received implies that the gods’ spirits are part of the ethnographic relationships, rather than being abstract objects of research. How I care for and treat these sacred artefacts and their spiritual embodiments reflects how much I value my relationship with the fieldwork contributors who donated them to me. At the same time, treating these artefacts well

curates and heals the sense of discomfort I had in researching the taboo topic of deconsecration rituals without being totally cognizant of the effects it could have had on my relationships in Taiwan. Curating for talismans reminds us of a second order of things, namely the difficulty of worshipping appropriately and utilizing sacred material as part of teaching, researching, and exhibiting. The spiritual presences in my fieldwork gifts have made me humbler in being attentive and negotiating them in my research and curatorial work, instilling doubts and forging creative ways to engage with sacred matter and its sensitive potential. I hope my words here could further sharpen other scholars' collections.

[1] Upon the publication of this contribution, I asked family Lin whether they wanted to remain anonymous or not, and they felt comfortable being named.

[2] In Chinese Buddhism, Guanyin is often depicted as either male or female, a gendered transformation of the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara following the introduction of Buddhism to China from India. Chinese folk religion, practiced by the Han ethnic groups across Asia, blends elements of Daoism, Buddhism, and Confucianism. Thus, it is not unusual for Daoist priests to run shrines dedicated to Guanyin, as is the case with the Lin family. In particular, Mr. Lin is a devout worshipper of one of Guanyin's incarnations, the Eighteen-Armed Guanyin Bodhisattva (十八手觀世音菩薩).

[3] For an extensive reference, refer to Chang, Hsun (張珣) (2006). 香之為物: 進香儀式中香火觀念的物質基礎 (Incense as a Thing: The Material Basis of the Incense Concept in Incense Offering Ceremony), 《臺灣人類學刊》 *Taiwan Journal of Anthropology* 4(2):37-73.

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